

FAIR Research Data and Workflows with EarthCODE

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Abstract. EarthCODE is a strategic ESA EO initiative to support the implementation of the Open Science and Innovation Vision included in ESA's 2024 EO Science Strategy. It federates EO cloud platforms, provides engineering support, curates FAIR research outputs (data, code, workflows, documentation), and builds an open-science community. The initiative helps scientists discover, visualize, explore, reuse, modify, and build upon research, and create reproducible workflows on EO cloud platforms – aiming to maximise the utilisation of data products and workflows for Earth Action.

Submission Type. dataset, infrastructure, project

BoK Concepts. [GC4] Open Science, [GD4] Data Quality, Metadata and Data Infrastructure, [GD2] Data Collection

Keywords. FAIR, Open Science, Earth Observation, Earth System Science, Cloud Computing, Reproducibility

1 Introduction

In 2024, the European Space Agency outlined its strategy for Open Science and Innovation—unlocking the full potential of Earth Observation for the benefit of society, from research to policy (European Space Agency (ESA), 2024). To achieve this, there is a requirement to provide high-quality Earth observation data, computing infrastructure to process it, and scientific methods to analyse the data, gain insights, and drive policy decisions from it.

The Open Science movement has emerged as a key enabler of sustained cross-institutional collaboration, supported by global programmes (AGU, 2024; Murphy, 2021) and reinforced through international policy guidance (European Union, 2020). To establish a

sustainable and effective Open Science practice, the FAIR principles have been adopted as core ideology for published digital objects.

EarthCODE (European Space Agency (ESA), 2026a) is an ESA initiative that supports the Open Science movement in Earth System Sciences. The initiative helps scientists publish, discover, explore, reuse, modify, and build upon EO research outputs, enabling reproducible workflows on cloud-based EO environments and improving the utilisation of EO science mission data products for Earth Action.

2 Earth Science Collaborative Open Development Environment (EarthCODE)

At its core, EarthCODE is a scientific community-focused ecosystem. First, the ecosystem integrates a wide range of available EO cloud computing platforms and services, including engineering support; it catalogs and manages the FAIR and open data, code, and documentation from ESA Earth System science studies and experiments; Second it builds a community of practice of Open Science in Earth Observation science.

2.1 Tools and Infrastructure for FAIR & Open Science

To provide modern, cloud-native Earth Sciences research environments, EarthCODE relies on the services provided by already mature EO Platforms and cloud computing infrastructures. For the initial batch of integrated platforms, EarthCODE has selected the CDSE openEO federation, Euro Data Cube and DeepESDL, alongside Insula and Geohazards Exploitation platforms selected in 2025. EarthCODE provides a central portal as a single-entry point to the federation of platforms. It provides single sign-on, access to EO data, tools to develop and

execute workflows, publication to the Open Science Catalog, and cross-platform re-execution of published experiments.

Integration is achieved via a federated architecture based on open components such as the “Interoperable Building Block Evolution Framework” (EOEPKA+) (EOEPKA, 2021) which provides open-source Building Blocks based on OGC standards and to which EarthCODE is a utilization domain. To further remove boundaries for reproducibility and open science - ESA provides sponsorship to computing and storage resources on these platforms via the Network of Resources (NoR) (European Space Agency (ESA), 2026b) for eligible projects. The Open Science Catalog (OSC) (European Space Agency (ESA), 2026c) is EarthCODE's central platform for publishing, discovering, and accessing EO data, workflows and documentation.

The OSC leverages open-source geospatial technologies like stac-browser, pycsw, PySTAC, and OpenLayers and tries to contribute back to these projects in terms of software and standardization (Schindler et al., 2023). The osc python library complements the OSC by providing a programmatic interface to search for and access catalogued research data for analysis.

2.2 Earth Observation Community Collaboration

EarthCODE enables the coordinated collaboration of the EO community through a variety of initiatives. First, through integration into the EarthCODE ecosystem, platform providers and engineering teams work together on shaping best practices for FAIR and reproducible science—both through day-to-day federation integration work and through broader initiatives such as the “Open Science Persistent Demonstrator” (OSPD) (Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), 2023). The OSPD is an OGC pilot focused on workflow portability across heterogeneous Earth Observation platforms. The initiative harmonizes the implementation of FAIR workflow principles – defining machine-readable descriptions (inputs, parameters, execution environment, provenance) using OGC building blocks and APIs.

EarthCODE directly supports publishers to package and publish their research on the Open Science Catalog. This support typically includes transforming research outputs into cloud-optimised formats where required and generating and validating the metadata needed for FAIR compliance. This has been a key focus and early success of EarthCODE, with published datasets such as WAPOSAL (Open Science Catalog, 2026) and SMART-CH4 (Open Science Catalog, 2025), and others under journal review.

As illustrated in Figure 1, a Product in EarthCODE is linked to an Experiment, which records the execution context required for reuse, including input datasets, workflow references, and runtime configuration. For example, the WorldCereal experiment published in the OSC generates cropland and crop type maps from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, links to an openEO workflow and associated code, records the configuration and execution assumptions used on the target infrastructure, and publishes the outputs as a Product described as a STAC (Spatio Temporal Asset Catalogue) Collection (Open Science Catalog, n.d.). Together, Products, Experiments, and Workflows capture both what was produced and how it can be reproduced.

Figure 1. EarthCODE Metadata Standards.

EarthCODE works closely with ESRIN and the Science Hub as well as the wider ESA community to provide practical training and hands-on support in EO engineering. It also engages the broader EO community through regular workshops, conference sessions, and technical talks and training at major Earth Observation events. In parallel, EarthCODE maintains and evolves a set of best-practice guidance for FAIR and Open Science across data, workflows, and publication in the EarthCODE ecosystem (European Space Agency (ESA) EarthCODE, 2026).

3 Future Work

EarthCODE is delivered through three workstreams (Infrastructure, FAIR Open Science, Community), procured annually and embedded in ESA's FutureEO Programme. ESA provides governance and the reference architecture, while platform partners run the federation and maintain the open-source building blocks. The current phase focuses on platform integration and publishing experiments to the Open Science Catalog; Phase 2 deepens interoperability via EOEPKA+ with future plans to create agentic tooling to streamline discovery, metadata generation, and reuse.

3.1 Data and Software Availability Section

All data products, software, and associated artefacts supporting this work are available through the EarthCODE platform and the Open Science Catalog (OSC).

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have not used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

References

AGU: Open Science, AGU, available at: <https://www.agu.org/learn-about-agu/about-agu/open-science>, last access: 05 January 2026, 2024.

EOEPKA: Master System Design Document: EOEPKA.SDD.001, available at: <https://eoepka.github.io/master-system-design/current/>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2021.

European Space Agency (ESA): Earth Science in Action for Tomorrow's World: Earth Observation Science Strategy, ESA, 42 pp., October 2024, 2024.

European Space Agency (ESA), 2026a: EarthCODE (Earth Science Collaborative Open Development Environment), available at: <https://earthcode.esa.int/>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2026a.

European Space Agency (ESA), 2026b: Network of Resources (NoR) – NoR Discover, available at: <https://nor-discover.org/>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2026b.

European Space Agency (ESA), 2026c: Open Science Catalog (OSC) – Catalog, available at:

<https://opensciencedata.esa.int/catalog>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2026c.

European Space Agency (ESA) EarthCODE: Data and Workflow Best Practices, EarthCODE Documentation, available at: <https://esa-earthcode.github.io/documentation/Community%20and%20Best%20Practices/Data%20and%20Workflow%20Best%20Practices/>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2026.

European Union: EU Open Science Policy, available at: <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science>, last access: 05 January 2026, 2020.

European Union: EU Open Science Policy, available at: <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science>, last access: 05 January 2026, 2020.

Murphy, K.: Open-Source Science: The NASA Earth Science Perspective, *The Earth Observer*, 33, 5, 4–9, 2021.

Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC): Open Science Persistent Demonstrator (OSPD) Initiative: Call for Participation, Version 1.3, November 2023, available at: https://portal.ogc.org/files/?artifact_id=106421, last access: 05 January 2026, 2023.

Open Science Catalog: SMART-CH4, <https://doi.org/10.57780/esa-6d202e9>, available at: <https://www.doi.org/10.57780/esa-6d202e9>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2025.

Open Science Catalog: WAPOSAL, <https://doi.org/10.57780/esa-1ab8cf3>, available at: <https://www.doi.org/10.57780/esa-1ab8cf3>, last access: 09 January 2026, 2026.

Open Science Catalog: WorldCereal, available at: <https://opensciencedata.esa.int/experiments/worldcereal-experiment/record>, last access: 08 April 2026, n.d.

Schindler, F., Pari, S., Meissl, S., Smith, G., Dobrowolska, E., and Angheloa, A.: Open Science Data Catalogue, *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci.*, XLVIII-1/W2-2023, 997–1003, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-1-W2-2023-997-2023>, 2023.